

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FINE AND APPLIED ARTS IN CULTIVATING ELEGANCE IN BUILDING AN ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical foundations of the socio-philosophical analysis of the place of fine and applied arts in building an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan, the socio-cognitive potential of fine and applied arts in building an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan, the future tasks of developing fine and applied arts in building an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan. Also, the issues of developing fine and applied arts in building an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan are analyzed.

Key words: building an enlightened society, integration, art, socio-spiritual basis, perspective, fine arts, applied arts, artistic-creative potential, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis.

Introduction. Art is a collection of artistic works, in which the artistic reflection of reality occurs based on the principles of artistic creation, style, and method. The concept of style emerged much earlier than the concept of method. Some art critics regard style as a law of form, a collection of methods and tools unrelated to content, thereby absolutizing form. In reality, artistic style is a structural unity with content. Artistic style requires the unity and relative moderation of certain formal components.

The concept of style is also explained by the internal connection between form and content. As style is manifested through form and content, it selects a particular method of creation. Just as artistic style cannot exist without the method of creation, the method of creation cannot be expressed without artistic style. In short, the method of creation and artistic style are interrelated concepts.

Analysis of literature and methods. Regarding the spiritual foundations and social functions of art, art education, and its spiritual potential, researchers such as P. Van Hauve, D. Kerven, Y. Jacque-Dalcroze, L. Daniel, F. Lissek, R. Muenix, D. Karomatli, E. B. Abdullin, B. M. Teplov, A. N. Soxor, V. G. Mozgot, V. I. Petrushin, B. V. Asafey, V. Beloborodova, T. V. Cherednichenko, S. F. Gurbanaliev, E. Abdulin, Y. Bodina, N. Ivanov, A. Nizamov, V. Rajnikov, F. Khalilov, D. Soipova, O. A. Ibrohimov, D. Karimova, R. Khonazarova, S. Makhmudova, M. S. Mukhitdinova, Z. Oripov, SH. Omanqulova, Q. Panjiev, R.

Azizov, X. A. To'raqolov, M. Khojdaeva, G. Sharipova, U. Y. Yuldoshev have conducted research.

Results and discussion. The method of creation is the collection of rules for the artistic evaluation and generalization of reality, while artistic style is the collection of rules for creating form. In order to understand the essence of artistic style, it is necessary to grasp the characteristics of the creative method. Key characteristics of artistic style include the harmony between external and internal delicacy, the infallibility of the sense of proportion, the strict proportionality of parts, and the completeness of unity.

The relationship between artistic style and method has a historical character, as they function differently at various stages of society and art. In medieval European art, the artistic method called classicism set strict boundaries in the selection of artistic tools corresponding to the life objects and events chosen by the artist. As a result, the classical method merged with artistic style.

In the art of realism, a different relationship between style and method can be observed. The realistic creative method expands the scope of artistic reflection of reality, necessitating the manifestation of various individual styles and even requiring different stylistic solutions in artistic works. This does not mean that the realistic method leads to the arbitrariness of artistic styles, but rather opens a broader way to understand the logic of reality and to express it through artistic means.

While artistic style has an independent status, it originates from certain creative methods. A single method can be expressed through several styles. Works of authors such as Navoiy, Mashrab, Qodiriy, Oybek, Cholpon, Abdulla Oripov, and Erkin Vohidov, created in the realistic method, are examples of this.

The concept of artistic style can be applied to a specific artistic work, an individual artist's creation, a particular movement or trend, or a certain genre. For example, when discussing the artistic style of A. Qodiriy's "O'tkan kunlar" or Cholpon's "Kecha va kunduz," it can easily be stated that these works were created in the "realistic method." In these works, the artistic style reflects the internal unity of the various components of form. Thus, style always indicates artistic integrity and relative moderation. Artistic style is most clearly demonstrated through a particular genre. A genre-specific style refers to the system of artistic expression tools specific to that genre. Tragedy, novel, or sculpture has its own set of visual-expressive tools. These works have their own

unique plot type, artistic structure (composition), and tonal qualities. One could describe the style as the “physiognomy” of the genre itself.

The components that manifest the genre style in different types of art have unique characteristics. In the field of oral (verbal) creation, the plot, artistic structure, and in theatrical works, the actor’s performance, the relationship between the actor and character, and the rules for placing actors on stage hold special significance. In certain genre styles, there are traditional genre measures, for example, the placement of syllables and stress in poetry, the rules of tempo, rhythm, and accent in music (maqom), and so on. Genre style also actively influences the artistic process. When an artist continues the traditions of a particular genre, it first begins with genre style. The artist can introduce innovation into a genre, enrich it, or sometimes reconstruct or alter it.

One of the historical forms of artistic style is the national style, which encapsulates the most general rules inherent to the artistic culture of a particular nation or people. National style is formed based on the social and historical conditions of a people’s life. In national style, national spirit, culture, and traditions are emphasized. The eternal and enduring elements of a people’s life are embodied in national style. Artistic traditions, especially the folk oral tradition, play a crucial role in its formation.

National style is closely related to the national characteristic of art. Although national style is one of the most important elements and indicators of national characteristics, it does not replace the national characteristic itself. While the national characteristic encompasses all areas of art, national style refers to the key principles of the artistic form that reflects the people’s life and national spirit. National style includes the musical tonality, poetic forms, performance practices, decorative art patterns, color tones, thematic melodies, national plots, artistic structures, folk genres such as ghazals, fairy tales, anecdotes, epics, proverbs, national stories, songs, marches, and others, which are characteristic of a particular artistic culture.

The concept of artistic style is also explained by the notion of stylistic direction. Stylistic direction refers to the common stylistic features inherent to the artists of a certain artistic movement. Stylistic direction consists of worldview, hopes and aspirations, creative principles, and individual stylistic tendencies.

As the primary form of artistic style, individual style or the author’s style is gaining increasing prominence. Not all artists are able to create their own individual style, as it is a rare occurrence. Only those with exceptional talent,

who have left a deep mark on humanity's artistic development, create their "style" and stand out distinctly from others.

The individual style is not isolated from the "general style." One can observe the features of a particular genre or artistic style through the analysis of the works of the most talented artists. There are cases where some gifted artists, through their "individual style," break free from the boundaries of a particular genre or movement and create new traditions by violating the established rules of that genre and style.

In individual style, the unity of artistic language, tone, rhythm, artistic structure, and so on is defined by the unity of the author's attitude toward reality. The moral-aesthetic approach to reality forms the artistic idea of the artist's creation, constituting the basis of their "individual style." The uniqueness and breadth of the artist's personality define the distinctiveness of their authorial style.

The "individual styles" of great artists differ from one another; they may even be diametrically opposed in terms of form. Some styles are filled with metaphors and comparisons, while others are inclined toward direct depiction, some are concise and brief, while others are characterized by expansive narration. However, the expressive and visual means of the style are manifested depending on the artist's artistic idea, how they reflect life, and their thought processes. In creating their style, the artist refines their thoughts and seeks deeper ways to represent life. In realistic art, creating a style means discovering artistic truth and expressing it in a unique way.

The artistic style of an artist is directed towards encouraging the viewer, reader, or listener to think independently and evoke a sense of pleasure. When the author's thoughts are clear and expressed smoothly, the style also becomes refined. Here, the sense of style plays a crucial role, as it pertains both to the artist and to those who benefit from their work. The artist's sense of style is manifested in their ability to find the artistic form, distinguish between primary and secondary elements, and vividly convey the concepts of good and evil. For the viewer, reader, or listener, the sense of style means recognizing the author's personality hidden beneath the unified form.

Even artists with a unique style draw on existing stylistic traditions and rely on the stylistic explorations of other artists. Every artist experiences the "torment of searching for words."

The concept of artistic style (method) broadly refers to the system of creative paths and tools. Artistic method is the set of ideological and aesthetic

principles upon which the artist bases their process of expressing, generalizing, and evaluating reality through expressive means.

Although artistic methods are characteristic of the creative work of a number of artists, they may also appear in a unique form in the work of individual artists. Artistic methods—the basic principles of creation, the quality characteristics—are interrelated and may either substitute for one another, work side by side, conflict with each other, or even suppress each other. Artistic method is fully manifested in the directions of artistic creativity.

Conclusion. Artistic method has a historical content and is related to the artistic directions in various types of art. The concepts of "artistic method" and "artistic directions" are so closely linked that sometimes their boundaries are not easily distinguishable. In the history of art, movements like classicism, romanticism, critical realism, realism, and new realism all require the existence of corresponding types of artistic methods. Both artistic methods and artistic directions are shaped and developed under the significant influence of political, philosophical, aesthetic, and religious beliefs. The emergence of new creative methods reflects profound shifts in the development of humanity's artistic consciousness.

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